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The Effect Of Dietary Factors [*Ascorbic acid, citric acid, orange juice and tea*] On The Bioavailability Of Non Haem Iron From White And Whole Meal Flour - *In Vitro*

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ABSTRACT

Anaemia as an increasing disease has gained lots of attention. Fe deficiency affects more than two billion people in the world. Low dietary iron intake takes most response of that consequence. In order to increase Fe availability, the effects of different dietary environments need to be studied. In this experiment, the diffusibility of two kinds of flour (white and wholemeal) dietary non – heme iron in five different conditions (ascorbic acid, citric acid, combination of ascorbic acid and citric acid, orange juice and tea. The diffusible iron was determined through creating physiological condition that is similar with stomach and small intestine. 1,10-phenanthroline method is used to value the amount of diffusible iron. The results show that white flour has higher iron absorption rate than wholemeal flour without any additive. And for white flour, ascorbic acid, citric acid, the combination of ascorbic acid and citric acid and orange juice contribute the iron absorption, , for wholemeal flour, the combination of ascorbic acid and citric acid, tea and orange juice are good enhancers. Thus, this experiment reveals promoters and inhibitors of iron absorption.

Keywords: heme iron, wholemeal flour, diffusibility

INTRODUCTION

Iron is an essential mineral that play a vital role in the physiological functions of the human body and as such, adequate intake of iron from the daily diet is indispensable for the maintenance of good health. It acts as a cofactor or as structural component for numerous enzymes and proteins required for many biological processes. Although needed in minute amount by the body, inadequate intake and/or poor absorption can lead to a variety of disorders such as iron deficiency anaemia (Nishito and Kambe, 2018). When ingested together in the same meal, dietary factors can either enhance or inhibit the absorption of iron. Meat, fish and poultry enhance the absorption of heme iron and inhibited by calcium (Hunt, 2005). In addition to these two, several other dietary factors influence non-heme iron absorption. Absorption enhancing factors include ascorbic acid, citrate, organic acid, amino acid, fructose and alcohol. Absorption inhibiting factors include phytate and fibre from legumes, grains, vegetable protein (in soya beans and nuts), tannins and other polyphenols in tea, coffee and red wine.

The main objective of this experiment is comparing different factors' effect of iron absorption, determining the types of substances that work as an inhibitors or promoters of iron absorption in the dietary environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw materials

The whole meal, white meal flour, ascorbic acid, citric acid, orange juice and tea were obtained from the sokoto central market.

Reagents

Pepsin suspension

Pepsin suspension was prepared on a fresh day by dispersing pepsin powder (16.0g Fisher scientific UK Ltd) in to 0.1M HCl in a 100ml stoppered measuring cylinder.

Pancreatin-bile extract mixture

To prepare 1 litre, pancreatin (4.0g pig pancreas BHD chemicals Ltd poole England) and bile extract (25.0g porcine Sigma chemicals Co.) were dissolved in 800ml 0.1M sodium bicarbonate and the volume was made up to 1L with 0.1M sodium bicarbonate.

2M sodium acetate

Sodium acetate(2M) was prepared by dissolving 272.16g of sodium acetate in distilled water and the volume was made up to 1L.

10% hydroxylammonium chloride

To prepare 250ml, 25.0g of hydroxylammonium chloride was completely dissolved in 250ml distilled water.

0.25% aqueous 0-phenanthroline

0-phenanthroline solution (0.25%) was prepared by dissolving 0.5g 0-phenanthroline in 150ml distilled water in a beaker and placed on a magnetic stirrer/heat plate at about 75⁰C until completely dissolved and the volume was adjusted to 200ml.

5µg Fe/ml solution

Iron solution was prepared in a fume cupboard by dissolving 0.272.16g of Ammonium iron (II) sulphate hexahydrate in 500ml distilled water, 2 drops of conc. HCl were added and diluted up to 1L in a volumetric flask. 50ml was taken out of this solution and further diluted to 1L in a volumetric flask and the final solution is 0.005mg Fe/ml (5µg Fe/ml).

EDTA solution for dialysis tubing

EDTA solution (0.01M) was prepared by dissolving 7.40g EDTA, 40.0g sodium bicarbonate and 2g Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) in 2L of distilled water. Segments of dialysis tubing (MWCO 12-14000 Daltons, 19.0 mm; Medicell Membranes Ltd, Unit A, Teatro Tower, Creek Road London) was added to the 0.01M EDTA solution, split over 1L x 1L beakers and boiled for 10 minutes, the tubing was rinsed 5 times with distilled water and boiled for another 10 minutes in distilled water. The tubing was allowed to cool and used for dialysis.

Analytical method

Digestion and dialysis

The released of diffusible iron was determined according to the method described by Miller *et al.* (1981). Twenty grams of each sample was mixed with 80ml distilled water and homogenized by a blender to a creamy consistency. The pH of the homogenates was adjusted to 2.0 with 6M HCl. Pepsin suspension(3ml) was added to each homogenate and incubated in a shaking water bath at 37⁰C for 90 minutes. Duplicate 20g samples of the pepsin digest were then transferred in to 50ml plastic centrifuge tubes. Segments of dialysis tubing containing 20ml distilled water and 1.5ml 0.5 mol. L NaHCO₃ were placed in each centrifuge tube. The centrifuges were then incubated in a shaking water bath at 37⁰C for 30 minutes. Pancreatin-bile extract mixture(5.0ml) was added to each tube and incubated further for 90 minutes. At the end of the incubation time the dialysis tubes were removed and the content of the diffusate were measured and analysed.

Measurement of the diffusible iron

To determine the amount of diffusible iron, the 1, 10-phenanthroline method was used. 10.0 ml distilled water was added to 10 ml diffusate. The pH was adjusted to pH 3-6 with 2M sodium acetate solution and using Congo Red Paper as an indicator. 0-phenanthroline solution(4ml) was added, and the volume was made up to 50 ml using distilled water. The samples were mixed and left to stand at room temperature for 10 minutes before absorbances were measured at 510 nm against distilled water.

The amount of iron in the diffusate was derived from iron standard curve ranging from 0-100 µg Fe. The standards were made up and measured in the same way as the diffusates, only that 5.0 ml of hydroxylammonium chloride solution (10% w/v) was added before adjusting the pH to 3-6.

The percentage diffusibility was calculated as below:

$$\% \text{ Diffusibility} = \text{Iron content in diffusate} / \text{Total Iron content in homogenate} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

All statistics were conducted using Microsoft Excel version 2013.

Due to limited samples sizes i.e. n= 3, non-parametric tests were used i.e. Kruskal-Wallis and pairwise Mann-Whitney post hoc tests.

The following significance levels were used in the analyses p<0.05(*), p<0.01(**) and p<0.001(***)

RESULTS

1. Iron content in diffusate

$$I = (D \times H) / 10 = \mu\text{g Fe in diffusate}$$

Table 1 Iron content in diffusate in different conditions

Condition	Iron content in diffusate(μg)		
	Sample A	Sample B	Average
	14.026	14.210	14.118
White flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	14.5	13.5	14.0
	16.026	13.816	14.921
	9.474	11.053	10.264
Wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	8.947	7.737	8.342
	6.842	9.395	8.118
	5.132	9.474	7.303
white flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	25.658	34.737	30.2
	40.732	34.863	37.80
	36.316	39.237	37.78
	38.132	42	40.07
wholemeal flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	8.421	16.184	12.30
	13.579	9.947	11.76
	7.184	11.053	9.12
white flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	24.316	23.737	24.03
	23.158	38.789	30.97
	20.132	24	22.07
	40.895	38.5	39.70
Wholemeal Flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	9.474	8.289	8.88
	8.289	7.184	7.74
	10	10.5	10.25
white flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	40.460	43.105	41.78
	42.726	38.084	40.40
	44.210	46.421	45.32
	85.789	67.895	76.84
wholemeal flour + 300mg	31.5	32.5	32.00

Ascorbic Acid + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	36.497	33.158	34.83
	8.5	11.053	9.78
White flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	8.421	10	9.21
	13.816	14.737	14.28
wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	14.068	10.579	12.32
	16.316	11.564	13.94
white flour + 80 cm ³ Orange Juice	36.474	32.132	34.30
	33.158	32.105	32.63
	45.053	45.474	45.26
wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ Orange Juice	24	16.413	20.21
	28.947	22.105	25.53

The iron content in diffusate of white flour and wholemeal flour in different conditions are shown in table 1. The results are presented as raw data and mean.

2. Iron content in homogenate

$K = C \times J / B = \mu\text{g Fe per weight of sample from homogenate} = \text{total Iron content in sample}$

Table 2 Total iron content in homogenate

Condition	Total Iron content (μg)		
	Sample A	Sample B	Average
White flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	81.97	81.90	81.94
	82.63	82.83	82.73
	82.02	81.71	81.86
	82.46	81.64	82.05
White flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	80.82	81.01	80.92
	81.68	81.74	81.71
	81.24	81.48	81.36
	75.37	75.60	75.48
White flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	81.61	81.54	81.58
	80.74	80.69	80.72
	81.61	81.65	81.63
	81.14	81.22	81.18
White flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 300	82.62	82.10	82.36

mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	81.78	81.68	81.73
	81.25	81.27	81.26
	81.98	81.97	81.97
White flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	81.86	81.55	81.70
	81.78	81.73	81.75
	82.40	82.60	82.50
White flour + 80 cm ³ Orange Juice	77.61	77.67	77.64
	79.13	79.16	79.14
	81.51	80.67	81.09
Wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	179.48	176.87	178.18
	176.06	175.84	175.95
	162.81	165.50	164.16
Wholemeal flour + 300 mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	176.56	176.40	176.48
	177.69	177.35	177.52
	81.27	81.28	81.28
Wholemeal flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	176.40	176.27	176.33
	176.51	177.23	176.87
	176.89	176.96	176.93
Wholemeal flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 300 mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	175.32	175.46	175.38
	175.92	176.60	176.26
Wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	176.08	175.98	176.03

Table 2 shows the total iron content in two homogenatesamples ofwhite flour and wholemeal flourin different conditions. The results are presented as raw data and mean.

3. % diffusibility in different conditions

$$\% \text{ Diffusibility} = (\text{Iron content in diffusate} / \text{Total Iron content in sample}) \times 100 = (I / K) \times 100$$

Table 3 % diffusibility in different conditions

Condition	% diffusibility	Average	SD	CoV
White flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	17.23	16.22	2.20	0.14
	16.92			
	18.23			
	12.51			
Wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ distilled water	4.68	4.58	0.10	0.02
	4.61			
	4.44			
white flour +	37.32			

300mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	46.26	45.78	5.61	0.12
	46.44			
	53.09			
wholemeal flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	6.97	8.27	2.09	0.25
	6.62			
	11.22			
white flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	29.46	38.14	7.01	0.18
	38.37			
	35.81			
	48.90			
wholemeal flour + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	5.04	5.07	0.58	0.11
	4.38			
	5.79			
white flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	50.73	62.42	18.24	0.29
	49.43			
	55.77			
	93.74			
wholemeal flour + 300mg Ascorbic Acid + 300mg Citric Acid + 80 cm ³ distilled water	18.25	19.00	0.76	0.04
	19.76			
White flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	11.97	13.52	2.70	0.20
	11.27			
	17.31			
wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ Tea	7.00	7.39	0.39	0.05
	7.78			
white flour + 80 cm ³ Orange Juice	44.18	47.07	6.29	0.13
	41.23			
	55.81			
wholemeal flour + 80 cm ³ Orange Juice	11.66	13.18	1.52	0.12
	14.70			

The % diffusibility of white flour and wholemeal flour in different conditions are shown in table 3. The results are presented as raw data, mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and Coefficient of Variation (CoV). According to table 3, the values of CoV in %diffusibility of white flour and wholemeal flour in different conditions ranged from 0.02 to 0.29, wholemeal flour in normal condition had the smallest value of CoV in %diffusibility, whereas white flour in the condition of adding with ascorbic acid and citric acid had the biggest value of CoV in %diffusibility.

Table 4 Effects of different dietary factors on the diffusibility of dietary non – heme Iron from White and Wholemeal flour

Flour type	different conditions	% diffusibility
White flour		
Control		16.22±2.20
Ascorbic acid		45.78±5.61 #
Citric acid		38.14±7.01 #
Ascorbic acid+ Citric acid		62.42±18.24 #
Tea		13.52±2.70
Orange Juice		47.07±6.29 #
Wholemeal flour		
Control		4.58±0.10 *
Ascorbic acid		8.27±2.09
Citric acid		5.07±0.58
Ascorbic acid+ Citric acid		19.01±0.76 #
Tea		7.39±0.39 #
Orange Juice		13.18±0.52 #

Note: ★ means P< 0.05 as compared with white flour in normal condition

means P< 0.05 as compared with corresponding control(normal condition)

The effects of different dietary factors on the diffusibility of dietary non-heme Iron from white flour and wholemeal flour are shown in table 4. The results are presented as mean ± standard deviation. In normal condition, the % diffusibility in white flour is considerably greater than that in wholemeal flour(P< 0.05), demonstrating that iron absorption rate in white flour is higher than that in wholemeal flour.

For white flour, the % diffusibility in the condition of adding ascorbic acid, or citric acid, or in combination with ascorbic acid and citric acid, or orange juice is significantly higher than that in normal condition(P< 0.05), suggesting that these factors are enhancer of iron absorption. Additionally, the

% diffusibility in the condition of adding tea is lower than that in normal condition, but there is no significant difference ($P > 0.05$), indicating that tea has little effect on iron absorption of white flour.

For wholemeal flour, though the % diffusibility in the condition of adding ascorbic acid or citric acids higher than that in normal condition, there is no significant difference ($P > 0.05$), indicating that ascorbic acid or citric acid alone has little effect on iron absorption. However, the % diffusibility in the condition of adding both ascorbic acid and citric acid is significantly higher than that in normal condition ($P < 0.05$), suggesting that these two factors together obviously enhance iron absorption through a additive or synergic effect. Orange juice is also an enhancer of iron absorption, which is similar to white flour. In contrast to white flour, tea exerts an enhancing effect on iron absorption of wholemeal flour.

4. Relative enhancement factor

$$\text{Relative Enhancement factor} = \% \text{ diffusibility Flour} + \text{condition} / \% \text{ Diffusibility Flour} + \text{water}$$

Table 5 Relative enhancement factor

Condition		Relative enhancement factor
	Ascorbic acid + water	2.8 times fold increase
	citric acid + water	2.2 times fold increase
White flour +	ascorbic acid + citric acid + water	3.8 times fold increase
	orange juice	2.9 times fold increase
Wholemeal flour +	ascorbic acid + citric acid + water	4.1 times fold increase
	tea	1.6 times fold increase
	orange juice	2.87 times fold increase

Table 5 shows the increase in absorption for iron content depending on the different dietary factors used. For white flour, enhancers are ascorbic acid, citric acid, the combination of ascorbic acid and citric acid and orange juice. For wholemeal flour, enhancers are the combination of ascorbic acid and citric acid, tea and orange juice.

DISCUSSION

The absorption of dietary iron depends on the interaction between the ingested form of iron and the dietary matrix, and upon the absorptive capacity of the enterocytes lining the luminal surface of the gut under high a degree of physiological control (Hunt, 2005). The use of in vitro estimation of diffusible iron is based on the principle of measuring soluble iron, and the recently used of the “physiological” techniques are proved to be more successful due to their ability to reflect the result obtained from human studies (Hazell and Johnson, 1987).

In this study a modified version of Miller et al., (1981) has been used, a unique technique in which the events occurring when food leaves the stomach and enters the duodenum were mimic inside the dialysis tubing and high molecular weight soluble complexes are also excluded. However, the values obtained for the diffusible iron should be considered as a relative indication of diffusible iron rather than absolute because the exact physiological condition cannot be reproduced and the physiological factors accounting for the major variations in the digestion and absorption of iron cannot be simulated. Nevertheless, the method should be able to reproduce accurately the effect of identified enhancer and inhibitor in vivo.

In the present study it can be seen from table 4 that in the control condition, the % diffusibility of iron in the white flour is considerably greater than in the wholemeal flour at 95% level of confidence. This is attributed to the high concentration of bran and fibrin the wholemeal flour. Bran is rich in phytate which strongly binds iron making it unavailable for absorption. Phytate inhibits iron absorption in a dose-dependent fashion and even a small amount has a marked effect (Itske et al., 2000). Our result is similar to other studies that reported lower diffusibility of iron in wholemeal flour (Halberget al., 1989. Russender-Hulthen et al., 1990). It can also be observed that in the two samples the % diffusibility is higher than the normal ($P < 0.05$) following the addition of ascorbic acid. This is because non-heme iron is available as ferric iron which is not readily absorbable. As a reducing agent ascorbic acid reduces ferric iron to ferrous form thereby facilitating its absorption from the gastrointestinal tract. Ascorbic acid also counteracts the effect of dietary phytate and tannin to form an iron-chelate complex making iron more available for absorption (Fishman et al., 2000). Our results agree with the findings of Adrienne and Marvin (1990). Addition of citric acid enhances the diffusibility of iron in the two samples of flour. This is because citric acid is an effective chelating agent, forming soluble complexes with iron which increases its absorption (Coulter, 2009). It can be seen that (table 4) the combined effect of citric acid and ascorbic acid is far more effective than the individual effects signifying a possible synergistic effect. Our result is like another previous study that reported an effectively combined effect of citrate and ascorbate (Hazell and Johnson, 1987). The role of orange juice as an enhancer of iron diffusibility is attributed to its high concentration of both ascorbic acid and citric acid. This clearly indicates that both the natural and synthetic form of ascorbic and citric acid can positively influence iron absorption (Itske et al., 2000). Our findings agree with the result of Hazell and Johnson (1987) that reported high diffusible iron in orange juice treated flour. On the other hand, the condition in which tea was added for the white flour is lower than that of the normal condition. This is because tea polyphenols and flavonoids have the iron binding capacity. Formation of the Iron-flavonoids complexes decrease iron solubility (Itske et al., 2000). However, tea is seen to have an enhancing effect (table 4) for the wholemeal flour at $P < 0.05$. This contradicts the existing literature and as such requires further investigation.

From table 5. It can be observed that both citric and ascorbic acids are good enhancers of Iron absorption, but ascorbic acid is more effective. This might be due to the role of ascorbic acid as both reducing and chelating agent. It can also be observed that the combined effect of ascorbic acid and citric acid is far more effective (3.8 times fold increase for white flour and 4.1 times fold increase for whole meal) indicating a possible synergistic mechanism.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results obtained, it can be concluded that ascorbic and citric acid are effective enhancers of iron diffusibility for the white meal and whole meal flours. However, the enhancing potential of the two (citric and ascorbic acid) combined and that of orange juice is far more effective. Future research should focus on the effect of tea on the absorption of the dietary iron.

REFERENCES

- Coulter, T. 2009. Food The chemistry of its components. *Royal society of chemistry fifth edition*. pp.446-449.
- Fishman, S.M., Christian, P and West, K.P. 2000. The roles of vitamins in the prevention and control of anemia. *Public health nutrition*.3(2), pp.125-150.
- Hallberg, L., Brune, Mand Rossander, L. 1989. Iron absorption in man: Ascorbic acid and dose-dependent inhibition by phytate. *Am. J. Clin. Nut.* **49**, pp.140-144.
- Hazell, Tand Johnson, I.T. 1987. In vitro estimation of iron availability from a range of plant foods: Influence of phytate, ascorbate and citrate. *Brit. Jour. Nut.* **57**, pp.223-233.
- Ho, P. T., Khan, N. C., Van, B. C., Gross, R., Conde, W. L and Dui, K. H. 2005. Milk fortified with iron or iron supplementation to improve nutritional status of pregnant women: An intervention trial from rural Vietnam. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*. **26**(1), pp.32-38.

- Hunt, J.R. 2004. Dietary and physiological factors that affect the absorption and bioavailability of iron. *Int. J. Vitam. Nut. Res.* **75**(6), pp.375-384.
- Itske, M.Z., Onono, K and Lilian, B.M.T. 2000.Effect of tea and other dietary factors on iron absorption.*Clinical Reviews in Food Sci. and Nut.* **40**(5),pp.371-398.
- Miller, D.D., Schricker, B.R., Rasmussen, R.R and Van, C. D. 1981. An in vitro method for estimation of iron availability from meals.*Am. J. Clin. Nut.* **34**, pp.2248-2256.
- Rossander-Hulthen, L., Gleerup, A and Hallberg, L. 1990. Inhibitory effect of Oat products on non-hemeiron absorption in man. *Eur. J. Clin. Nut.***44**,pp.783-791.